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“HER YET”

When asked if she knew, she boldly said yes
When she speaks, they ignore
Yet she shares

When asked if she sings, she said yes
When she sings, they frown
Yet she delivers

When asked if she dances, she said yes
When she dances, they flee
Yet she goes

When asked if she draws, she said yes
When she draws, they cover
Yet she finishes

When asked if she plays, she said yes
When she plays, they laugh
Yet she continues

When asked if she cooks, she sweetly nods
When she cooks, no one tastes
Yet she happily offers

In her every yes, she gambles
In every gamble, she fell short
Yet her confidence stays strong.

